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Abstract

Examines ethical and relational challenges when therapists work within their own queer communities. Discusses countertransference management, professional boundary maintenance, and navigation of dual relationship dynamics. Offers a framework for culturally safe practice that honors community connections while preserving therapeutic integrity, recognizing particularities of care in contexts where shared identities influence the clinical process.

Keywords

clinical practice, psychodynamic, cultural competence

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